

Molecular gas accreting onto massive high-z galaxies

INAF Osservatorio
Astronomico di Roma

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

Michele Ginolfi
2^o year PhD

Collaborators:

Paris - June 2017

R. Maiolino

S. Carniani

T. Nagao

P. Santini

A. Marconi

R. Schneider

F. Belfiore

G. Cresci

F. Mannucci

A. Pallottini

Questions driven by observations

$$\text{SFR} \sim 10^2 - 10^3 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$$

$$\tau_{\text{depl}} = \frac{M_{\text{gas}}}{\text{SFR}} \sim 300 \text{ Myr} - 1 \text{ Gyr}$$

SF occurs on longer timescale!

mini bibliography

Leroy+08
Sancisi+08
Cresci+09
Genzel+10
Tacconi+13
Saintonge+13
Schinnerer+16

but star formation sequence is evident at all times....

Additional gas reservoir is needed to support star formation

Galaxies contain <10% of baryons, an huge reservoir is available in the IGM.

Accretion of gas from the IGM can supply galaxies at all epochs (especially at high-z)!

What we know from simulations...

Let's make just a two points...

- In the early Universe massive galaxies grow via **accretion of gas** through cosmic streams.
- Gas accretion fuel the **intense SF** observed in such primeval systems.

mini bibliography

Dekel et al. 2009
Genel, Dekel & Cacciato 2012
Silk & Mamon 2012
Sanchez Almeida et al. 2014
Keres et al. 2014
Nelson et al. 2015
Ceverino et al. 2016
Sanchez Almeida et al. 2017

The pursuit of observational evidences

J. Werk, UCSC

Cresci+10

Indirect Way

'Inverse' metallicity gradients

The central gas may have been diluted by the accretion of primordial gas.

Via Emission

Cantalupo+14; Borisova+16; Fumagalli+16;
Patricio+16; Wisotzki+16; Vanzella+16;
Vernet+17

What we know from simulations...

- Gas in these streams should also **cool and collapse to form stars**, enriching the streams with metals, even before accreting onto massive galaxies.

Dekel et al. 2009
Nelson et al. 2015
Danovich et al. 2015
Ceverino et al. 2016

- Streams show gas clumps of mass of the order of 10% of the central galaxy.
- The $> 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ clumps, are also gas rich. 30% of their baryons turn into stars before they merge with the central galaxy.

This scenario opens up new possibilities...

1) Gas in the flowing streams may somehow get "self-enriched"

+

2) IGM/CGM enrichment is particularly enhanced in overdense regions (e.g. protoclusters) due to the large presence of massive outflows (starburst and/or AGN driven)

...see Tuesday afternoon talks:

- 1) star formation enhancement
- 2) ~20 more AGN than in the field

Under these peculiar conditions, cold gas flows may be investigated exploiting the classical tracers of star formation, metallicity and molecular gas

ALMA observations

ALMA (CO J=4-3) of the **most massive galaxy** in the redshift range $3 < z < 4$ within the 150 arcmin^2 covered by the GOODS-S field.

CANDELS-5001 belongs to the **AMAZE** sample (Maiolino et al. 2008)

metallicity, stellar mass, SFR, morphology etc...

near-IR spectroscopy - **SINFONI**

optical and near-IR imaging - **HST**

mid-IR photometry - **Spitzer**

$$z = 3.473$$

$$M_{\text{star}} \sim 1.9 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$$

$$Z \sim 1/2 Z_{\odot}$$

$$\text{SFR} \sim 200 - 250 M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$$

Ginolfi et al. 2017

Troncoso et al. 2014; Santini et al. 2015

Candels-5001 is located in a large-scale overdensity of galaxies
(likely a forming protocluster)

Franck & McGaugh 2016: based on a $\delta(\text{gal})$ selection criteria

Forrest et al. 2017: extreme [OIII] + H β emitting galaxies overdensity

Lemaux et al. (in prep): extreme overdensity of star formation and stellar mass in the density maps from the VUDS spectroscopic survey

Len Cowie (private communication): huge excess in the 850 μ flux (SCUBA-2)

ALMA observations

OBSERVATIONS AND DATA REDUCTION

To trace the molecular gas, the field was observed with ALMA targeting the **CO J=4-3** rotational transition (redshifted to 103.1 GHz)

- band 3: [90-106] GHz
- field of view (Primary beam) ~ 60"
- 30 antennae (12 m)
- max baseline: 1.2 Km
- angular resolution: ~ 1" (Briggs)
- integration time: ~ 2 hr
- rms: 9.5 μ Jy/beam (continuum),
0.3 mJy/beam (datacube 20km/s)

configuration tailored at detecting molecular gas down to deep sensitivity on large scales!

Extended CO emission

The CO emission is extended over about 40 kpc in an elongated structure (NE-SW).

Total gas mass of the system:
 $M_{\text{gas}} \sim 1 - 6 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$

uncertainties: CO J=4-3/CO J=1-0 $\alpha(M - L_{\text{CO}})$

Only the 30% of the mass is associated with Candels-5001

something similar...

Ginolfi et al. 2017
Candels-5001, $z=3.47$

Emonts et al. 2017, Science
Spiderweb galaxy, $z=2.15$

Extended CO emission

position-velocity diagram

The kinematic "suggests" that the gas in CGM is tracing accreting radial streams onto the central massive galaxy.

Moreover...

We detect
CO emitting systems
up to **~250 kpc!!!**
...mostly distributed in
the same NE-SW
direction!

- ☉ significance > **5 σ**
- ☉ positive/negative
ratio = 10
(**<10% contamination**)

CO emitters gas masses
 $M_{\text{gas}} \sim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$

some objects may be galaxies belonging to the overdensity (the velocity spread is comparable with the velocity dispersions observed in other high- z protoclusters)

Casey et al. 2015 Chiang et al. 2015

some others have velocities compatible with tracing large scale streams terminating onto the massive galaxy!

let's have a look to simulations...

Simulation tailored at reproducing the same properties of our target

Dekel, Lapiner: private communication

Conclusions

- I have shown ALMA observations (CO J=4-3) tracing the molecular gas around (...on CGM scales) the **most massive galaxy** at $z \sim 3-4$ in the GOODS-S field.
- We reveal **streams of molecular gas** on scales from 40 to 200 kpc accreting onto the central galaxy. (see **Ginolfi+17**)
(First **direct evidence of cold flows?** we need confirmation and more statistics)
- I'm planning follow-up observations (ALMA, MUSE, SINFONI).

My idea:

This may be a common behaviour among massive galaxies in overdense regions (e.g. protoclusters).

These are peculiar systems where it may be possible to understand gas accretion by looking at the molecular gas phase.

Thanks for your attention

